

Polysemantic relationships of geological terms in English and Uzbek languages and their comparative analysis

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Abstract. The article reflects the concepts of the term and gives its interpretations. The article introduces the concept of polysemy and the role of polysemy in the geological system. The opinions of some scientists were expressed in this regard. In this terminological system, increased polysemy, homonymy, synonymy and antonymy phenomena were identified and comparative guides were prepared in Uzbek and English.

Keywords: terminology, terminological polysemy, neologism, texture analysis, terminological system.

Полисемантические отношения терминов геологии в английском и узбекском языках и их сравнительный анализ

Аннотация. В статье рассмотрено структура термина и даются его толкования. А также представлено понятие полисемии и роль полисемии в геологической системе. По этому поводу были приведены мнения некоторых ученых. В этой терминологической системе выявлены явления усиленной полисемии, омонимии, синонимии и антонимии, созданы сопоставительные справочники на узбекском и английском языках.

Ключевые слова: терминология, терминологическая полисемия, неологизм, текстурный анализ, терминосистема.

Introduction. All sciences and areas of the world do not shy away from constant dynamic change and gradual development. In this sense, neither language, which is considered a means of human communication, nor the lexical level of language are excluded from this process. If we look into the past, geology as a science arose on the basis of practical activities of people and continues to develop day by day. Therefore, the formation of terminology in the field of geology is inextricably linked with information about rocks, minerals, ores in general and layers of underground resources since the distant past. In the distant past, in addition to pure metals such as iron, copper, gold, silver and bronze, people could also find ores rich in tin and copper compounds. They also tried to solve the problems of the formation of the earth, rocks, land distribution and seas. The Greek philosopher Thales believed that everything around us originated from water and then turned back into water. Mil. a V. In the 6th century, fossilized shells of marine mollusks were found on the mountain peaks. Strabo (63 BC - 20 years of the 1st century AD) believed that the earth was constantly changing, moving and sometimes rising, creating islands and continents, great mountains and sometimes sinking again. There is also geological terminology of terms denoting objects and their use[4]. We considered it appropriate to analyze them into the following groups, taking into account the following:

Materials and methods. Analyzing the stages of the formation of geological terminology on the basis of scientific and historical sources, we considered it permissible to periodize the development of the lexical units related to the subject as follows. At this point, based on the opinion of above-mentioned scientist, the following theoretical conclusions were drawn, to which we should attach importance in the formation of the geological terminology of the Uzbek language. 1. Foreign scientific words and terms must be fully translated into Uzbek; 2. It is appropriate to

leave the untranslated words unchanged only when it is impossible to find a complete alternative (equivalent) to the Uzbek word or when it is widely used as a word borrowed from a foreign language;3. In this case, it is correct to give the foreign term a form specific to the Uzbek language. At the same time, it is important to select words from new lexical units with the correct meaning, using the composition of the national vocabulary of the literary language in the formation of new terms. For example: in English: observation, phenomenon, acid, fire glass, earth's axis, air pump, experience, movement, particle, fire-breathing mountain, laws of motion, refraction of rays, balance of bodies, slaked and quicklime, specific gravity, magnetic needle, etc. In Uzbek: observation, event, acid, stained glass, globe, air pump, experiment, movement, particle, fiery mountain, laws of motion, refraction of rays, balance of bodies, slaked and quicklime, specific gravity, magnetic needle, etc[2].

Results. The terms acid and magnetic needle in the Uzbek examples above can be an example of our second theoretical conclusion. In the 19th century, geology developed rapidly as an independent science. In turn, the number of lexical units making up geological terminology has increased and improved. During this period, terms such as: bank, reef, underwater plateau, young platform, anthropogenic relief, asymmetry of relief, buried relief, river terrace, fossil relief, coral structure, coral reef, channel, adjacent reef appeared in the languages of the world, especially in English, dunes lexical units such as coast, reef, underwater plateau, young platform, anthropogenic relief, asymmetry of relief, buried relief, river terrace, fossil relief, coral structure, coral reef, channel, border, reef dunes appeared in the geological terminology of the Uzbek language. At the same time, when systematizing the terminology of mining and geology, it was important to use the term in accordance

with the content of a particular concept, to create special explanatory dictionaries that reveal the functional-semantic boundaries. As a result, in 1841 the “Mining Dictionary” was published in Russian for the first time in Russia. This dictionary contained approximately 3,800 terms in the fields of geology, metallurgy, chemistry, physics, mechanics and civil engineering[4]. Thus, the publication of this dictionary contributed to the creation of the first complete system of mining and geological terminology in Russia at that time, organized in Russian, alphabetically.

Discussion. Thus, the publication of this dictionary contributed to the creation of the first complete system of mining and geological terminology in Russia at that time, arranged alphabetically in Russian. The next period of rapid development of the geological terminology corresponds to the last quarter of the 19th century. This period can be seen as an important stage in the emergence and gradual development of geosciences, more precisely geology. The terms of this period testify to the development of all scientific and technical ideas in the geological industry and indicate the systematic and progressive organization of terminology. As a result, the geological terminology is as follows: *crater hole, crater layer, crack, peat relief, accumulation terrace, steppe accumulation plain, orogen - orogeny (formation of a mountain), denudation - denudation), plateau denudation, abrasive platform - abrasive (peak-shaped) coasts, abrasive platform, anticline – anticlinal structure (a ridge-shaped fold of layered rocks in which the layers slope away from the summit), the valley of the U-shaped valley, mouth - mouth (place of a river).), Couloir - gorge (a steep, narrow gorge on a mountain slope), mesorelief - mesorelief (relief forms whose height amplitude usually does not exceed a few tens of meters) with an average size between macro-relief and micro-relief forms (valleys of small rivers,*

ravines, side ridges, moraine hills, sand dunes, mud volcanoes, etc.) mountainous terrain, blocky mountains, accumulative shore and other field terms were added[10].

In Uzbekistan, there are still not enough textbooks and training manuals in Uzbek covering the science of geology, which is a natural science. For example: “Dictionary of Geology” by O. Sodikov (T., 1958), G\'.O. Mavlanov, G.A. Utyushev's “Dictionary of Russian-Uzbek geological terms” (T., 1978) is, firstly, printed in a few copies, secondly, they do not contain complete explanations of technical terms and, thirdly, understand the meaning of new terms and conceptual neologisms that have appeared in the last 35–40 years in have entered our language. does not fully meet the ever-increasing needs of readers. In view of this, T.N. in 1995 “Russian-Uzbek explanatory dictionary of geology”, consisting of 240 pages, was compiled under the authorship of Dolimov. The dictionary contains more than 2,500 of the most commonly used geological terms and, in our opinion, can be considered the first comprehensive geological terminology dictionary[7].

Not long after, in 2007, under the authorship of scientists such as B.A. created the “Russian-Uzbek explanatory dictionary of geological terms”. Isakhodjaev, M.U. This dictionary contains more than 7,400 definitions of geological concepts, i.e. terms. However, there is no need to explain that the lack of a perfect dictionary covering the English and Uzbek geological terms shows how important our research is. During this period, word acquisition is also important for the development of the geological terminology of the Uzbek language. Therefore, we found that most of the field terms came from the English language, but entered the Uzbek language through the middle Russian language and adapted to the phonetic and grammatical rules. We felt it necessary to provide an example of these borrowed terms below. For example: *USB. Minus, Plus, Diameter, Radius, Formula, Barometer, Horizon, Ecliptic,*

Microscope, Meteorology, Optics, Horizontal, Vertical, Periphery, etc.; Russian Minus, Plus, Diameter, Radius, Formula, Barometer, Horizon, Ecliptic, Microscope, Meteorology, Optics, Horizontal, Vertical, Periphery; visual minus, plus, diameter, radius, formula, barometer, horizon, ecliptic, microscope, meteorology, optics, horizontal, vertical, periphery[8].

If the above geological terms were formed in the English language in the 18th century, we can observe that they were widely used in the terminology of various areas in the Russian and Uzbek languages at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century. Century. The number of lexical units in geological terminology is proportional to the amount of knowledge and skills acquired at the historical stages of development of the field. Because as expertise increases, the need for new words and terms also increases. In most cases, this need is met through the acquisition of words and terms from different subject areas and the creation of new words and terms. The numerical growth of geological terminology in the English and Uzbek languages is closely related to the general development of the lexical fund of the literary language in both languages. It has been observed that the stages of development of geology-related units in English and Uzbek languages are inextricably linked with time and system in both languages. Although the use of geological lexical units in the Uzbek language and the English language goes back a long time, some of them were used as international terms as early as the 19th and 20th centuries.

It should be noted that new periodical publications, educational and scientific literature, the emergence of new specialties, as well as the rapid development of science and technology ensure that the process of concept formation is somewhat disorganized and disordered[9].

Conclusion. Therefore, as a result of our analysis, we present three scientific views that are directly related to the formation of geological terms: 1) field terminological units formed on the basis of the current English and Uzbek literary languages; 2) terminology of other languages, firmly established in the English and Uzbek languages and mastered by the people; 3) Using the terminology of other languages to create new terms in both languages, i.e. word acquisition is effective in forming geological terminology.

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